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SYNTHESIS OF TRITHIOCARBONIC ACID ESTERS AND STUDY OF THEIR TRIBOLOGICAL AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to a current problem of the present time, which consists in the creation of new highly effective additives for transmission oils and antioxidants for fuels.

A number of new trithio acid esters have been synthesised, containing two arylsulpho groups (bis-trithiocarbonates, as well as a combination of one arylsulpho group and allyl and benzyl fragments in one molecule (mixed trithio acid esters).

The resulting mixed esters of trithiocarbonic acids were studied as anti-wear and extreme pressure additives.

The tribological properties were studied in a semi-synthetic oil, which was a mixture of MC-20 aviation oil and PEE (pentaerythritol ester) synthetic oil taken in a 1:1 ratio.

Due to the limited solubility of bistrithiocarbonates in mineral oils, they were studied as antioxidants for fuels. The antioxidant properties of the compounds were studied using a special manometric setup.

The composition and structure of the synthesised compounds were confirmed by studying their physicochemical properties, elemental composition and IR spectroscopy.

Keywords: bistrithiocarbonates, antioxidant properties, tribological properties, transmission oils.

Introduction

Trithioacetic acid forms two series of neutral esters: asymmetrical ones, with different radicals at each sulphur atom, and symmetrical ones, with identical radicals at both sulphur atoms.

Trithioacetic acid derivatives are structurally similar to dithioacetic acid derivatives and differ only in the presence of an additional sulphur atom in the molecule instead of an oxygen atom. Therefore, both asymmetric and symmetric trithioacetic acid esters can be synthesized using methods similar to those used for synthesizing dithioacetic acid esters. However, it should be noted that trithioacetic acid esters, including the methods for their production, are much less studied than dithioacetic acid esters.

The main methods for obtaining dithioacetic acid esters can be used for the synthesis of trithioacetic acid esters.

One of them involves the interaction of mercaptans with chloroformates in the presence of alkalis:

The disadvantage of this method is the multi-stage nature of obtaining the initial chloroformate and the duration of the reaction, which takes 16-19 hours [1].

A more convenient classical method for obtaining asymmetric and symmetric esters of trithioacids is the interaction of mercaptans with carbon disulphide in the presence of alkalis:

Where, R=C₄H₉, C₅H₁₁; R' = R'' = C₂H₅, C₄H₉

As studies of the tribological properties of compounds have shown, all synthesized compounds have high extreme pressure properties in transmission oil [9].

Mustafaev N.P. et al. synthesized bis(alkylthiomethyl)trithiocarbonates by reacting sodium trithiocarbonate with alkylthiomethyl chloride:

Где, R=C₄H₉, C₅H₁₁

Continuing our work on the synthesis of trithio acid esters and their study as additives for various purposes, we synthesized a number of new trithio acid esters containing 1 or 2 arylsulpho groups.

The scheme of the compounds synthesised by the authors of the article is presented below:

Synthesis of various arylsulfotriithiocarbonates by reaction of arylsulfoxylides with sodium trithiocarbonate.

Experimental part

The uniqueness of the compounds obtained was proven by determining their elemental composition, elements C, H, S, were determined using a TruSpec-Micro analyser (LECO), refractive index (n_D^{20}), specific gravity (d_4^{20}) with subsequent calculations of MRD

found and MRD calculated and their comparison, as well as IR spectroscopy.

IR spectra were recorded on a SPECORD-75 IR spectrophotometer (Carl Zeiss, GDR) using KBr, NaCl and LiF prisms in the range 4000÷400 cm⁻¹.

Trithioacetic acid salts are similar in structure and chemical properties to xanthogenic acid derivatives. However, it should be noted that, unlike xanthogenic acid esters, trithioic acid esters have not been fully studied. Therefore, the synthesis of new compounds from a series of trithiocarbonic acid esters and their study, in particular the inclusion of an arylsulpho group in the molecule, is of particular interest, since trithiocarbonates with this group were first synthesised and studied by us. Sodium sulphide, phenyl- and toluene-

sulphochlorides, allyl bromide and benzyl chloride are used as starting materials for the synthesis of these substances. Phenyl- and toluene-sulphochlorides and sodium trithiocarbonate were synthesised by the authors.

Synthesis of aryl sulphochlorides from the reaction of aryl sulfonic acids with phosphorus pentachloride.

These starting materials were obtained by the known method according to the following scheme [10]:

Preparation of benzenesulphochloride:

In a flask connected to a cooling bath, 15.7 (0.1 mol) benzenesulphonic acid and 20.6 g (0.1 mol) of phosphorus pentachloride are added and heated at 120°C for 30 minutes. After the mixture has cooled, 200 ml of benzene is added to the flask, and the mass is heated again at 80°C for 1 hour. The benzene and POCl₃ are then evaporated. The obtained substance is a liquid. Yield – 82%. $n_D^{20} = 1.5480$

The elemental analysis of the substance is as follows:

C₆H₅SO₂Cl: Found, %: C 45.85; S 20.38; H 3.18

Calculated, %: C 45.07; S 20.23; H 3.12

Preparation of toluenesulphochloride:

The toluenesulphochloride used as the starting material was prepared by us using the known method, employing toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH·H₂O) and phosphorus pentachloride:

In a flask connected to a reflux condenser, 34.4 g (0.2 mol) of toluenesulphonic acid and 41.2 g (0.2 mol) of phosphorus pentachloride (PCl₅) are added and heated at 120°C for 30 minutes. After the mixture has cooled, 200 ml of benzene is added to the flask, and the mass is heated again for 1 hour at 80°C. The benzene and POCl₃ are then evaporated, and the crystals remaining in the flask are p-toluenesulphochloride. Yield – 75%. Tmp = 64.5°C.

The elemental analysis of the substance is as follows:

C₇H₇SO₂Cl: Found, %: C 43.92; H 3.52; S 16.63; Cl 18.48

Calculated, %: C 43.1; H 3.68; S 16.8; Cl 18.64

p-Toluenesulphobenzyltrithiocarbonate (III) [11]

Toluenesulphobenzyltrithiocarbonate is obtained from the reciprocal synthesis of toluenesulphochloride and benzyl chloride with sodium trithiocarbonate:

The reaction to obtain toluenesulphobenzyltrithiocarbonate was carried out in two stages:

Stage I. Preparation of sodium trithiocarbonate

To a 7.8 g (0.1 mol) of sodium sulfide, stirred in 40 ml of water in a reaction flask, is added 7 ml (0.1 mol) of carbon disulfide. The reaction mixture is stirred

for 1 hour at 30-35°C. Stirring is then continued for a further hour at 40-45°C.

Stage II. To the resulting aqueous solution of sodium trithiocarbonate, 8 g (0.05 mol) of toluenesulphochloride is added in portions and stirred at 60-65 °C for 3 hours, then 7.6 g (0.05 mol) is added dropwise and the mixture is stirred for 2 hours at 60-65°C. The result-

ing material is extracted with benzene, washed with water, and the benzene is evaporated. The resulting trithiocarbonate is a crystalline substance. Mp. -50°C .

The elemental composition of the substance is as follows:

$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}_4$: Found, %: C – 50.72; H – 4.15; S – 35.98

Calculated, %: C – 50.85; H – 3.96; S – 36.16

The chemical structure was confirmed by IR spectroscopy using an UR-20 instrument.

Figure 1. IR spectrum of *p*-toluolsulphobenzyltrithiocarbonate

In the IR spectrum of the substance, the absorption band for the valence vibrations of the CH bond on the aromatic nucleus is observed at 3041.85 cm^{-1} , and the absorption bands for the valence vibrations of the CH bond are observed in the 2963.50 cm^{-1} and 2738 cm^{-1} regions. The deformation vibration absorption band of this bond is not observed. Characteristic absorption bands of the aromatic nucleus are observed at 1593 cm^{-1} , 1488.50 cm^{-1} , and 1449 cm^{-1} . The absorption band of the C=S group of the trithiocarbonate is observed at 1078 cm^{-1} , that of the C–S group at 578 cm^{-1} , and the absorption band of the valence vibrations of the SO_2 bond at 1217 cm^{-1} .

Analogously, phenylsulphobenzyltrithiocarbonate (IV) was also prepared.

Mp. $-74-75^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The elemental analysis of the substance is as follows:

$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}_4$: Found, %: C 49.56; H 3.64; S 37.48

Calculated, %: C 49.41; H 3.53; S 37.65

Preparation of *p*-toluolsulfoallitrithiocarbonate (V) [12]:

First, 7.8 g (0.1 mol) of sodium triacetophenesulfonate is prepared in an aqueous solution in a reaction flask. Then, 7.6 g (0.04 mol) of toluene sulfochloride is added in portions. The reaction is stirred for 3 hours at $60-65^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then, 5 g (0.05 mol) of allyl bromide is added and the reaction is stirred for a further 4 hours at the same temperature. Benzene is then added to the flask, and the benzene-extractable material is washed with water. The benzene is removed and the residue is dried under vacuum. Mp. $133-135^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The elemental analysis of the compound is as follows:

$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}_4$: Found, %: C –43.28; H –3.82; S –41.92

Calculated, %: C–43.42; H–3.95; S–42.11

Figure 2. IR spectrum of *p*-toluolsulfoallitrithiocarbonate

In the IR spectrum of the substance, the absorption bands of the double bond valence vibrations are at 1724.68 cm^{-1} and 1682 cm^{-1} , and the absorption bands of the $\pi\text{-C}=\text{H}$ bond in the aromatic nucleus are at 3162 cm^{-1} , at 3063.52 cm^{-1} , at 3015 cm^{-1} , the valence vibration absorption band of the $\text{S}-\text{O}$ bond at 1178.83 cm^{-1} . The vibrational absorption band of the $\text{C}-\text{S}$ bond was observed in the 459.16 cm^{-1} region, and the deformation absorption band of the CH bond in the CH_2 group, CH , was observed in the 1474.71 cm^{-1} region.

Preparation of bis(phenylsulfonyl)trithiocarbonate (II):

Phosgene (17.6 g, 0.1 mol) is added dropwise to a 7.7 g (0.05 mol) solution of sodium trithiocarbonate in water in a reaction flask. The reaction is stirred for 5 hours at $60\text{-}65^\circ\text{C}$. Benzene is added to the resulting mixture and the benzene layer is washed with water, the solvent is evaporated and dried under vacuum. The resulting material is obtained as a crystalline solid. Mp. $69\text{-}70^\circ\text{C}$.

The elemental analysis of the material is as follows:

$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}_5$: Found, %: C-40.23; H-2.42; S-40.85

Calculated, %: C-40.00; H-2.56; S-41.03

Figure 3. IR spectrum of bis(phenylsulfo)trithiocarbonate

In the IR spectrum of the substance, the absorption bands of the CH bond are at 3150.69 cm^{-1} and 3067 cm^{-1} , the characteristic absorption bands of the CH bond of aromatic nuclei are at 1577.69 cm^{-1} . The absorption band of the valence vibrations of the $\text{S}=\text{O}$ bond

was observed at 1322.69 cm^{-1} , and the valence vibrations of the CH bond on aromatic nuclei were characteristic absorption bands at 1577.69 cm^{-1} .

Analogously, bis(toluolsulfo)trithiocarbonate (I) was prepared by this method.

The elemental analysis of bis(toluolsulfonyl)trifluorocarbonate is as follows:

$C_{15}H_{14}O_4S_5$: Found, %: C–43.23; H–3.18; S–38.12

Calculated, %: C–43.06; H–3.35; S–38.28

Figure 4. IR spectrum of bis(trifluoromethane)sulphotrithiophosphorocarbonate

The IR spectrum of the substance shows a characteristic absorption band of the aromatic nucleus at 1587 cm^{-1} , absorption bands of the ν_{C-S} bond at 815 , 652 , 661 cm^{-1} , for the SO_2 groups, the $\nu_{S=O}$ bond absorption bands were observed in the 1184.61 – 974 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{C=S}$ bond absorption bands were observed in the 1296.59 – 1118.96 cm^{-1} regions.

Results and discussion

Study of the tribological properties of some synthesized arylsulfonic acids

The reliability of operation of various machines and mechanisms plays a major role in the country's economy. Therefore, as mentioned earlier, the creation of high-quality new additives to lubricating oils, which directly participate in extending the service life of machines and mechanisms, is of great practical importance. One of such additives is trithiocarbonates. This work presents new arylsulfotrithiocarbonates that have not been previously described in the literature. It should be noted that in the relevant foreign literature there is much less information about trithiocarbonic acid esters than about dithiocarbonic acid esters. However, the Institute of Additive Chemistry has developed a fairly extensive material on this class of compounds as additives to lubricating oils. [13-17].

The extreme pressure properties were determined according to GOST 9490-75. The calculated indicators were the load wear index (LW₁) (*load wear index* – an indicator indicating the effectiveness of extreme pressure properties in the interval between the welding load and the seizing load; the higher this indicator the better), critical load (CL) (*seizing load* – the mode in which the oil film and sliding of rubbing surfaces becomes difficult; in this case, the hydrodynamic friction mode is replaced by a semi-dry friction mode), welding load (WL) (*welding load* – is the force at which the rubbing surfaces are not able to slide relative to each other; moreover, high specific loads cause critical increase in temperature in the direct contact zone, which, in turn, entails welding of the contacting surfaces).

The extreme pressure properties were studied on a four-ball friction machine (FBM-1) according to GOST 9490-75 on steel balls IIIХ-15 with a diameter of 12.7 mm and a rotation speed of the upper ball of 1420 rpm.

Table 1 shows the data for 5% samples of p-aryl-sulfotrithiocarbonates and, for comparison, allyl xanthogenatomethyltoluenesulfamide prepared in semi-synthetic oil, which is a mixture of base oil SN-1200 and PEE (pentaerythritol ester of carboxylic acids) in a 1:1 ratio.

Results of research into the tribological properties of aryl sulfotriocarbonates

№	Compounds	Concentration of samples in oil, %	Extreme pressure properties GOST 9490-75			Wear spot diameter, W_d , mm
			Load wear index, LW_1 , N	Critical load, C_1 , N	Welding load, W_1 , N	
1.	Semi-synthetic oil – SN-1200 yağı + PEE (1:1)	–	283	686	980	1,25
2.	Semi-synthetic oil + <i>p</i> -Toluenesulphonylbenzyltrithiocarbonate (III)	5	486	980	3096	0,85
3.	Semi-synthetic oil + <i>p</i> -Toluenesulphonylallyltrithiocarbonate (V)	5	500	980	3724	0,75
4.	Semi-synthetic oil + <i>p</i> -Phenylsulphonylallyltrithiocarbonate (VI)	5	548	980	3479	0,72
5.	Semi-synthetic oil + <i>p</i> -Phenylsulphonylallyltrithiocarbonate (VI) + 1,5% DF-11	3	–	–	–	0,62
6.	Allylsantogenatomethyltoluenesulphonamide (for comparison) 	3	363	784	1060	

As follows from the results of the study, all synthesized mono-arylsulfotriocarbonates possess high extreme pressure properties, as follows from the presented data, allyl xanthogenatomethyltoluenesulfamide synthesized by the same authors. They also surpass the weld load of the universal oils "Rossoil RZh" and "Rossoil Vedeshka" produced in Russia. Thus, the weld load (WL) of these oils is 1960 N and 1568 N, respectively [18]. The high extreme pressure properties of the synthesized aryl trithiocarbonates can be explained by the presence of reactive radicals (allyl, benzyl) at the sulfur atoms in the molecules, as well as the trithiocarbonate fragment, the composition of which includes two thiol and one thionic sulfur, which also play an important role in achieving high extreme pressure properties. To more clearly understand the mechanism of action of the additives, it is necessary to pay attention to what the surface layer of the metal surface is. Atoms located on the surface of a metal have free bonds that are not compensated by neighboring atoms. Because of this, the metal surface attracts atoms

or molecules of various compounds from the external environment. Thus, the molecules of the compounds are adsorbed on the metal surface. Adsorption can be physical or chemical.

During chemical adsorption, the polar ends of *p*-arylsulfotriocarbonates bind to the metal surface. Under high temperature and pressure, trithiocarbonates decompose into smaller products such as sulfur, mercaptan, and trithiocarboxylic acid. It is logical to assume that the interaction of trithiocarbonates with the metal surface leads to the formation of brittle and easily degraded iron sulfides. These sulfides then react with the metal surface, forming a protective layer. Protective layers consist primarily of metal sulfides and oxides.

Studies of the tribological properties of *p*-arylsulfotriocarbonates show that they possess superior extreme-pressure properties compared to xanthic acid esters. This can be explained by the higher sulfur content of trithiocarbonates, as illustrated in the figure 5.

Figure 5. а) тритиокарбонат, б) ксантогенат

According to the geometry of the molecules under consideration, only two of the three heteroatoms can simultaneously participate in bonding with the metal surface during adsorption. It is logical to assume that molecules adsorbed by more electronegative oxygen will be more firmly retained on the surface and, consequently, will have superior antiwear properties. Thus, trithiocarbonic acid esters exhibit superior extreme pressure properties. However, they do not possess antiwear properties.

However, it should be noted that the synthesized bis(arylsulfo)trithiocarbonates have very limited solubility in mineral oils. Therefore, bis(toluenesulfo)trithiocarbonate was studied as a fuel antioxidant.

The antioxidant properties of the synthesized bis(toluenesulfo)trithiocarbonate were studied in the

presence of the substance at a concentration of $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol/L and during the autoxidation of isopropylbenzene - cumene as a model hydrocarbon at 110°C (Fig. 6). Peroxide radicals are the main factor determining the oxidation process of hydrocarbons. The reaction of the test compound with cumene peroxide radicals was studied. For this purpose, cumene oxidation with azoisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was initiated by introducing the test substance: $T=60^\circ\text{C}$: $[\text{AIBN}]=2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/L; $[\text{InH}]=5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L (Fig. 7).

The results of the study of the kinetic parameters of bis(toluenesulfonyl)trithiocarbonate as an antioxidant are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Antioxidant properties of bis(toluenesulfonyl)trithiocarbonate			
Kimyövi birləşmənin formulu	at 60°C		at 110°C
	f	$K_7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ $l/mol \cdot s$	τ , minute
Bis(toluenesulfonyl)trithiocarbonat (I)	3,24	3,8	225
2,6-ditretbutyl-4-methylphenol ionol (for comparison)	2,0	2,10	150

As follows from the data presented in Figures 6 and 7, the studied compounds effectively inhibit the oxidation process by reacting with cumene peroxide radicals.

The stoichiometric coefficient (τ) was calculated from the induction period $-f$, which is equal to the number of oxidation chains terminating on one inhibitor molecule and its transformation products:

$$f = \frac{\tau - W_i}{[I_n \cdot H]_0}$$

where: W_i – initiation rate equal to $2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mol/(l-s), $[I_n \cdot H]_0$ – initial inhibitor concentration, mol/l.

To calculate the rate constant for the interaction of inhibitors with peroxide radicals $-K_7$, the oxygen uptake kinetic curves were transformed from $\Delta[\text{O}_2]$ -t coordinates to $\Delta[\text{O}_2]$ -t⁻¹ coordinates and by the tangent of the slope angle equal to [19, 20]:

$$tga = \frac{f \cdot K_7 \cdot [I_n \cdot H]_0}{K_2 \cdot [RH] \cdot W_i}$$

$$K_7 = \frac{tga \cdot K_2 \cdot [RH] \cdot W_i}{f \cdot [I_n \cdot H]_0}$$

$$K_2 = 1.51 \text{ l/mol} \cdot \text{s}; [RH] = 6.9 \text{ mol/l}$$

From the values given in the table, it can be seen that the kinetic parameters of the obtained (bistoluenesulfo)trithiocarbonate in the reaction with cumyl peroxide radicals ($f=3.24$, $K_7=3.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ l/mol $^\circ\text{C}$) are higher than those of ionol (ionol parameters: $f=2.0$, $K_7=2.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol $^\circ\text{C}$), the induction time τ – 225 min, the induction time of ionol τ – 150 min.

The synthesized compound is an inhibitor with a combined effect: it repels cumyl peroxide radicals and breaks the oxidation chain. It also catalytically decomposes the cumyl peroxide formed during the reaction into molecular products.

Figure 6. Kinetic curve of cumene autoxidation in the presence of (bistoluenesulfonyl)trithiocarbonate (I) ($T=110^{\circ}\text{C}$; $[\text{In}\cdot\text{H}]=5\cdot 10^{-5}$ mol/L (curve 0 without inhibitor)

Figure 7. Kinetic curve of the initiated oxidation of cumene in the presence of (bistoluenesulfonyl)trithiocarbonate (I) (60°C .); $[\text{In}\cdot\text{H}]=5\cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L; $[\text{AIBN}]=2\cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/l (curve 0 without inhibitor)

As mentioned, the task of antioxidants is to destroy peroxides, that is, to decompose them into inactive radicals. They neutralize free radicals by donating a portion of electrons. Antioxidant properties can be demonstrated by products of various classes of compounds, including organic sulfur compounds.

Sulfur antioxidants are a group of organic compounds that protect the environment from free radicals.

These include substances such as mercaptans ($\text{R}-\text{SH}$), sulfides ($\text{R}'-\text{S}-\text{R}$), disulfides ($\text{R}'-\text{S}-\text{S}-\text{R}$).

It is known that sulfur-containing substances, including xanthates and trithiocarbonates, decompose at high temperatures into alkyl mercaptans, sulfides, disulfides, alkyl esters of thiocarboxylic acids, etc. [21]. The (bistoluenesulfo)trithiocarbonate purchased by us also decomposes into the above-mentioned active molecules and decomposes the peroxides formed in the fuel

into less reactive or inactive radicals, which, as a result, prevent the growth of the peroxide chain.

It should be noted that high levels of sulfides and mercaptans in fuel form sulfuric acids during its oxidation, which cause corrosion of engine parts. However, at low concentrations, these compounds greatly slow down the oxidation of fuel. Their mechanism of action is that these compounds primarily interact with the peroxides formed and decompose them [22].

Conclusion

A series of new sodium trithiocarbonate-based trithiocarbonate esters containing arylsulfo groups have been synthesized.

Preliminary tribological studies have demonstrated the potential for using displaced trithiocarbonate esters containing arylsulfo and allyl or benzyl radicals, respectively, as extreme pressure additives for lubricating oils.

These studies revealed that *p*-toluenesulfo benzyl and allyl trithiocarbonates possess high extreme pressure properties without possessing antiwear properties. However, the studies demonstrated the possibility of improving the antiwear properties of these compounds by formulating them with the well-known multifunctional additive DF-11.

Their extreme pressure effectiveness has been demonstrated to be superior to that of xanthic acid esters.

It has been found that bis(toluenesulfo)trithiocarbonate, which has limited solubility in lubricating oils, exhibits relatively high antioxidant properties in fuels.

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